

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

EVALUATION OF EFFICACY OF FLUORIDE CONTAINING BIOACTIVE GLASS, TRICALCIUM PHOSPHATE AND CASEIN PHOSPHOPEPTIDE-AMORPHOUS CALCIUM PHOSPHATE DENTIFRICES IN THE TREATMENT OF DENTINE HYPERSENSITIVITY -A RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIAL.

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Abstract:

Aim: Dentine hypersensitivity can cause acute dental pain which affects quality of oral health. This study aimed to compare fluoride containing bioactive glass, tricalcium phosphate and casein phosphopeptide-amorphous calcium phosphate (CPP-ACPF) dentifrices on dentine hypersensitivity (DH) as home treatment.

Materials and method: A double-blind randomised controlled trial was planned in a single centre with a total of 99 hypersensitive teeth among 82 systemically healthy subjects with chief complaint of dentin hypersensitivity. These subjects were randomly allocated into three groups for administration of desensitising dentifrices containing three different ingredients: Group 1 – fluoride containing bioactive glass, Group 2 – fluoride containing tricalcium phosphate, Group 3 – fluoride containing CPP-ACPF. DH was evaluated at 3, 6 and 12 months post treatment during the recall visits. Airblast test, cold test, tactile test and subjective test using visual analogue scale of pain (VAS) score was used to assess the level of sensitivity pre and post treatment in all the three groups.

Results: All the groups showed significant reduction in sensitivity after 3 months post treatment ($p < 0.05$). At 3, 6 and 12 months follow up in all the three groups recurrence in sensitive sites was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). Inter group comparison showed group 3 as significantly higher relief in VAS pain score as compared to group 1 and 2 after 12 weeks follow up ($p < 0.05$). However, post 6 and 12 months follow up no significant difference in between the groups was seen ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: Fluoride containing bioactive glass, tricalcium phosphate and CPP-ACPF dentifrices are effective in reducing dentinal hypersensitivity.

Keywords: Bioactive glass, casein phosphopeptide, dentifrice, dentine hypersensitivity, desensitising agent, tricalcium phosphate, Toothpaste.

Introduction

Dentine hypersensitivity can result in sharp intense pain as a result of exposure of dentine to hot or cold stimuli. The pain is often acute in nature and can result in difficulty in oral intake thereby reducing overall quality of oral health. Repeated insults by acidic medium, apical migration of marginal gingiva exposing the root surface, faulty toothbrushing are the predisposing factors associated with the condition.¹ It is multifactorial in origin and various theories are established to understand the painful sensitivity. Hydrodynamic theory is a popular theory stating the role of peripheral stimuli which causes the fluid movement inside the dentinal tubules resulting in pain.²

The prevalence of hypersensitivity in India varies from 40-50 % in northern parts to 30 % in southern India.³ These prevalence studies give us an insight about the overall population suffering from the condition and how effective treatment strategies are required to combat the condition. Prolonged sensitivity can affect overall intake of food products, compromising both oral and systemic health of an individual. In office and home care is the treatment regime for DH. In office treatment like application of fluoride varnish like glutaraldehyde (GLUMA), laser treatment, are effective methods of reducing sensitivity.⁴ However, home care use of dentifrices are popular means of sensitivity reduction. Though home-care based DH regimen is an acceptable treatment plan but patients' compliance is an important factor in success of treatment related to home based products.

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Dentifrices with potassium nitrate, sodium fluoride are time tested dentine hypersensitivity reduction toothpastes.⁵The pathway of sensitivity reduction is through blocking the nerve endings passing through the tubules, occluding the tubules itself, protein precipitation and anti-inflammatory pathways.⁶ Surgical treatment involves coverage of exposed root surface or cementum by various root coverage procedures like coronally advanced flap, periosteal pedicle flap.^{7,8,9} Use of growth factors like platelet rich fibrin can be beneficial in achieving desired root coverage.^{10,11} Prevention and management strategies can be modifications in brushing techniques, use of chemical plaque control agents and diet modifications.¹²⁻¹⁶

Bioactive glass containing fluoride (BioMin)(Elsenz, Group Pharmaceuticals Ltd., India) contains high phosphate with small particle size of silica-based bioglass. These dentifrice adheres to the dentine and forms a hydroxycarbonate apatite layer which occludes the dentinal tubules and relieves the pain. It is associated with low abrasive index and has shown effective reduction in sensitivity.¹⁷ Tricalcium phosphate (TCP) can co-exist with fluoride in both aqueous and non-aqueous forms. It is precursor to hydroxyapatite and milled to create a functionalised TCP (fTCP) which has enhanced mineralization capacity.¹⁸ Karlinsey modified this functionalised TCP to create an acid-resistant mineral promoting remineralisation.¹⁹ Such property can be utilised in the treatment of dentine hypersensitivity. Commercially available Clinpro tooth cream 3M contains 950ppm sodium fluoride with fTCP.

Casein phosphopeptide –amorphous calcium phosphate (CPP-ACP) is basically calcium phosphate with remineralizing potential which contains calcium and phosphate ions. This bioactive material is derived from the milk protein casein having anticariogenic, remineralization potential. Its role in dentine hypersensitivity is based on deposition of high concentrations of calcium, phosphate and fluoride ions which occludes the dentinal tubules.²⁰ Modification of this biomaterial is CPP-ACP plus fluoride which is associated with increase release of fluoride ions which precipitates calcium and phosphates and help in dentine occlusion. Commercially, it is available as CPP-ACPF tooth cream (GC Tooth Mousse Plus - GC Corporation. Tokyo. Japan).

The present study aimed at comparison of three dentifrices of different composition - fluoride containing bioactive glass, tricalcium phosphate and CPP-ACPF in home-based treatment of DH. Null hypothesis was no significant difference exists in the reduction of DH in between three dentifrices.

Materials and method

Study design and participants

This was a randomised controlled parallel arm double blinded study. The study was conducted in a tertiary hospital from February 2019-January 2021. This was a prospective study and ethical clearance was obtained from Institutional ethical committee review board (IEC/2019/132). After ethical approval screening of subjects started and final enrolment was done once the written informed consent was obtained by each subject. Inclusion criteria were systemically healthy subjects between age group 18-55 years, subjects on supportive periodontal

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therapy with present complaint of hypersensitivity, hypersensitive teeth on labial of incisors, cuspids and buccal surfaces of bicuspid and first molars with exposed cervical dentine in periodontally healthy subjects with probing depth < 3mm.

Exclusion Criteria was presence of large restoration, deep dental caries, fractured teeth/restorations, allergy to with IgE casein or any other ingredient of toothpastes, active periodontal infections, prosthetic, orthodontic appliances, antibiotics and /or anti-inflammatory drugs administration, periodontal surgery in past 6 months, pregnancy/lactating mother, tobacco/alcohol intake.

Calibration

The clinician (SN) was trained for clinical examination of DH evaluation using airblast method. Visual analog scale for pain measurement was also calibrated by the clinician for intra-examiner reproducibility. The intraclass correlation coefficient was 0.98. All the examinations were performed by a single clinician.

Intervention

- Subjects to use either of the three desensitizing dentifrices was allocated into 3 groups
- Group 1- received fluoride containing bioactive glass (BioMin) (Elsenz, Group Pharmaceuticals Ltd., India),
- Group 2- Fluoride containing tricalcium phosphate (Clinpro tooth cream 3M)
- Group 3- fluoride containing CPP-ACPF tooth cream (GC Tooth Mousse Plus - GC Corporation. Tokyo. Japan).
- All subjects received scaling and root planing before the beginning of the study. Oral hygiene instruction included brushing of teeth twice daily for at least 1 minute with the dentifrice given to them.

Clinical examination

Each subject was screened at initial baseline phase. Once enrolled in the study at baseline, 3 months, 6 months and 12 months post treatment clinical examination was performed. Each appointment minimum of two to four hypersensitive teeth were examined using stimuli test namely tactile test, cold water test and air blast test.

Before the examination, the tooth was carefully isolated with cotton rolls and stimuli were applied to each hypersensitive tooth as complained by the subjects. The application of stimuli was according to standard method as illustrated in previous studies.^{21,22}

Tactile test –explorer at a constant force was passed perpendicular to the long axis of the tooth across the labial and buccal surfaces of the tooth. This procedure was repeated three times and then the final score was recorded.

Cold water test- a syringe was loaded with ice-cold water and 0.2 ml was slowly expelled on sensitive teeth after proper isolation.

Air blast test –a blast of air was directed through a three-way syringe for 1s from 10 mm distance at 40-65 psi, directed towards affected tooth.

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Each test was performed with 5 minutes gap and the response was reported on the following scale.²³

- 0 – no significant discomfort, awareness of stimulus;
- 1 – discomfort but no severe pain;
- 2 – severe pain during application of stimulus;
- 3 – Severe pain during and after application of stimulus.

Subjective test

Numeric scale (NS) of 11 numbered items arranged 0 to 10 in ascending order. 0 means no pain and 10 most severe pain was used to know their perception of pain towards intake of hot/cold liquid/solid food. Clinician (SN) explained this scoring and the subjects had to self- assess their pain. Similar scoring system was used in a study by Naoumet al.²⁴

Sample size determination

The sample size was determined based on the primary outcome of the study. Mean differences Airblast score was considered to be the primary outcome while cold test, tactile test and subjective test were secondary outcomes. According to study by Orsini et al. the expected mean difference airblast score was 1.00 ± 0.53 in experimental group and 0.59 ± 0.50 in control group.²³ Alpha error at 0.05, power of 80%, attrition rate of 20% unpaired t- test was done to determine the sample size, a minimum of 30 subjects in each group were required.

Randomisation

Sample was randomised using computerised random number generator (Graphpad) in 1:1:1 allocation ratio. This was done by the investigator (PS) and the subjects were enrolled in the study by clinician at the study site. Masking of the toothpaste was done by labelling all the 3 toothpaste with a white paper and giving detail of the principal investigator (SN) in case of emergency. The distribution of toothpaste was done by clinician (DD) who was not involved in any clinical or subjective examination at any point of study.

Application Instructions

All the subjects were instructed to brush twice daily with soft bristle toothbrush and toothpaste given to them for next 3 months.

Statistical analysis

Normality test was done using Komologov test. Anova test was performed for intergroup comparison and intragroup comparison was done using repeated measure Anova. Non –normally distributed data, intragroup comparison was measured by Wilcoxon signed rank test and intergroup using Kruskal –Wallis test. P-value of 0.05 was considered as statistically significant. All the test was carried out using Statistical package for social science (SPSS windows version 16, Chicago, IL).

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Table 1. Participant characteristics

Variables	Frequency	Percentage(%)
Age group		
Mean+_SD	48 ± 8.24 (18-55)	
<_35 years	28	34
>35 years	54	65
Gender		
Female	48	58
Male	34	41

Initially 90 subjects were enrolled in this study.8 subjects dropped out in follow up at 6 months and so were excluded from the study with final sample size as 82. Males and females participated with age group 18-55 years mean age .The study included a total of 99hypersensitive teeth (*Figure 1*) of which incisors, canines, premolars and molars were present. No adverse effects among any group of subjects were reported at any interval of time.

Table 2: Dentin Hypersensitivity Assessment Score between the groups:-

	Group 1 Bioactive glass	Group 2 Tricalcium Phosphate	Group 3 Casein phosphopeptide- amorphous calcium phosphate	P value
Airblast test Score				
Baseline	2.12±0.44	2.02±0.23	2.33±0.13	>0.05
1 month	1.33±0.72	1.23±0.65	1.24±0.52	>0.05
2 month	1.15±0.76	1.12±0.62	1.10±0.55	>0.05
3 month	0.78±0.72	0.93±0.64	0.92±0.46	<0.05

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6 month	0.72±0.56	0.91±0.43	0.88±0.42	>0.05
12 month	0.68±0.43	0.88±0.38	0.82±0.32	>0.05
Difference between baseline to 3 months	1.34±0.28	1.09±0.41	1.41±0.33	<0.05
Difference between baseline to 12 month	1.44±0.16	1.14±0.15	1.51±0.19	<0.05
Cold water test score				
Baseline	2.16±0.62	2.00±0.58	2.12±0.52	>0.05
1 month	1.18±0.63	1.16±0.72	1.17±0.68	>0.05
2 month	0.96±0.56	0.98±0.62	0.96±0.58	>0.05
3 month	0.88±0.44	0.96±0.61	0.94±0.54	>0.05
6 month	0.77±0.41	0.92±0.45	0.93±0.52	>0.05
12 month	0.75±0.38	0.88±0.41	0.85±0.51	>0.05
Difference between baseline to 3 months	1.28±0.18	1.06±0.03	1.18±0.02	>0.05
Difference between baseline to 12 month	1.41±0.24	1.12±0.17	1.27±0.01	>0.05
Tactile test score				
Baseline	0.61±0.65	0.72±0.70	0.62±0.60	>0.05
1 month	0.52±0.50	0.65±0.60	0.54±0.50	>0.05
2 month	0.45±0.40	0.55±0.50	0.45±0.55	>0.05
3 month	0.38±0.40	0.44±0.50	0.38±0.50	>0.05
6 month	0.17±0.20	0.20±0.25	0.18±0.25	>0.05
12 month	0.01±0.02	0.03±0.02	0.01±0.02	>0.05
Difference between baseline to 3 months	0.23±0.25	0.28±0.20	0.24±0.10	>0.05
Difference between	0.60±0.63	0.69±0.68	0.61±0.58	>0.05

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baseline to 12 month				
Subjective test Score				
Baseline	4.32±2.21	4.26±1.95	4.11±1.72	>0.05
1 month	3.32±2.11	3.52±1.94	3.22±1.90	>0.05
2 month	2.31±1.62	3.15±1.91	3.05±1.64	>0.05
3 month	1.32±0.34	2.16±1.92	2.18±1.67	>0.05
6 month	0.92±0.84	2.08±0.97	2.02±0.88	>0.05
12 month	0.88±0.34	1.98±0.65	1.94±0.89	>0.05
	3.00±1.87	2.10±0.03	1.93±0.05	<0.05
Difference between baseline to 3 months	3.44±1.87	2.28±1.30	2.17±0.83	<0.05
Difference between baseline to 12 month				

Each test scores are summarised in table 2. All the three dentifrices were effective in relation to percentage of score reduction from baseline to 3 months which was statistically significant ($p<0.05$). At 6 and 12 months follow up group 1 showed significant greater improvement in airblast test and subjective test scores compared to group 2 and 3. The mean percentage reduction in airblast and subjective test score was significantly greater for group 1 than group 2 and 3 ($p<0.05$). No significant difference was obtained in between group 2 and 3 in terms of any test scores at time interval.

The rate of response in relation to airblast test and subjective test decreased significantly in Group 1 ($p<0.05$) as compared with group 2 and 3. However in relation to cold water and tactile test no significant difference in rate of response was seen in between any groups ($p>0.05$) (table 3).

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Table 3: Rate of response in each group:

Test	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	P value
Airblast test	64.3	32.3	31.1	<0.05
Cold water test	62.4	81.5	81.7	>0.05
Tactile test	21.7	13.8	12.4	<0.05
Subjective test	78.6	53.6	52.2	>0.05

Discussion

The present study compared the efficacy of three dentifrices in terms of dentinal hypersensitivity reduction. Airblast, cold water, tactile and subjective test was done to compare the overall response rate. The subjects were followed for 12 months during their supportive periodontal therapy. In a systematic review by Oliveira et al. suggested use of mechanical, water and evaporative stimuli for evaluating dentinehypersensitivity reduction by dentifrices.²⁵In the present study all the three stimuli were used for evaluation.

A study in sensitivity and specificity of scales used in dentinehypersensitivity stated that highest sensitivity value of 81.9% was obtained for Numeric scale as compared to visual analogue (VAS), faces pain scale (FPS) and verbal evaluation scale (VES).In subjective assessment the present study also used Numeric scale for self-assessment by the subjects.^{26,27} Patel et al. in their study compared 5% fluorocalcium phosphosilicate (BiominF) with (8% arginine and calcium carbonate and a placebo toothpaste and found BiominF as more efficacious than the other two toothpastes .²⁸In our present study we found BiominF to have better response rate as compared to tricalcium phosphate and CPP-ACPF.No adverse effects were reported in any groups. All the test scores showed significant improvement in all the groups (p<0.05). Airblast and subjective test in particular showed better improvement in group 1.Similar result was obtained by Pereira et al. in their in vitro study on Biomin, Novamin and fluoridecontaining dentifrice.²⁹Also, the rate of response for airblast test was found to be 64.3 % in group 1 as 32.3 % and 31.1% in group 2 and group 3 respectively.

BiominF forms a layer rich in calcium and phosphate on the exposed dentinal surface which acts as a ready source of ions contributing to remineralization.This mechanism of formation of calcium and phosphate ions can occlude the dentinal tubules reducing the sensitivity.

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Furthermore, Biomin is basically an inorganic, amorphous melt-derived biocompatible glass compound rich in calcium, fluoride, phosphate, and silica. The active ingredient is the inorganic chemical fluoro calcium phosphosilicate. In addition to fluoride in the glass, it has three times higher phosphate content, which promotes fluorapatite formation and has lower silica and smaller particles which gives less gritty in texture, reduces abrasion and enamel wear, and penetrates effectively into the dentinal tubules for occlusion. This reduced abrasive property could have further contributed to reduction in DH. Drisko et al. stated that abrasive action of dentifrices can contribute to DH and low to non-abrasive dentifrice should be preferred as it helps in occluding tubules.³⁰

Post ultrasonic scaling sensitivity can be managed by use of mouthwashes and studies have suggested preprocedural use of mouthrinse also reduces aerosols contamination.³¹⁻³² Periodontal diseases can result in gingival recession and cause dentin hypersensitivity.^{33,35}

In such cases treatment of periodontal disease should be initiated along with management of dentin hypersensitivity.³⁶⁻³⁹

Kedzierawski et al. performed a national research network on management of dentin hypersensitivity and data was collected using questionnaire method. The study concluded that over the counter treatment was mostly preferred and 86% dentist suggested combination of products.⁴⁰

The reason for choosing these three dentifrices in the present study is the different mechanism of action of each dentifrice towards reducing the dentinal hypersensitivity; also no study till date has compared these three dentifrices efficacy in terms of clinical and subjective test performed in this study. It gives us an insight to the possible potential role of these toothpastes in reducing DH. Combination of these dentifrices as long term treatment approach can be a future research that needs exploration. Each dentifrice has its own advantage, bioactive glass and calcium phosphate initiates early mineralisation which can be used at initial DH treatment and then we can switch to functional tricalcium phosphate which has sustained action on occluding of dentinal tubules.

Guanipa et al. studied effect of casein phosphopeptide amorphous calcium phosphate fluoride and photobiomodulation on DH and found combination therapy to have greater efficacy than individual therapy.⁴¹ In the present study only single therapy approach was compared as we wanted to study the efficacy of dentifrices individually. However, this study suggests the benefits of combination therapy.

A meta-analysis by Bae et al. on role of desensitizing toothpastes and placebo revealed that potassium, stannous fluoride, calcium sodium phosphosilicate were found superior to placebo.⁴² In the present study no placebo or control group was designed as it will be unethical not to intervene with any treatment especially when it's a long term follow up of 12 months. Gupta et al. in their review on placebo in clinical trials suggested that it will be unethical, violation to the concept of clinical equipoise when proven effective therapy is available to have placebo groups and this concept was kept in view while designing the study.⁴³ Aggarwal et al. compared Fluoro calcium phosphosilicate bioactive glass with strontium chloride hexahydrate and calcium sodium phosphosilicate containing desensitizing dentifrice and found bioactive glass to give

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Superior results as it had early onset of action.⁴⁴We also found bioactive glass group to be better than other two groups and the onset of action might be a crucial mechanism favouring early relief from the DH symptoms.

Heft et al. have compared fluorocalcium phosphosilicate and calcium sodium phosphosilicate and found that fluorocalcium to be more effective in reducing DH.⁴⁵ The inherent property of fluoride containing bioactive glasses to release fluoride ions leads to fluorapatite formation. Calcium fluoride causes glass dissolution and higher phosphate content enhances the ability to form apatite crystal which instantly occludes dentinal tubules.

Zhou et al. used casein phosphopeptide and studied its remineralisation property in primary dentition.⁴⁶ They found that this calcium phosphate had remineralisation potential and this active agent has a diameter 20 times smaller than the diameter of the dentinal tubules, so a larger amount of calcium phosphate per area within the tubular canaliculi, thus obliterating them more effectively for a prolonged period. This could be a possible reason in reduction of DH seen in group 3 subjects.

Gilmer et al. suggested new perspective in management of DH and laid down guidelines and treatment strategies as no single approach can completely resolve the patient's complaint.⁴⁷ Furthermore, the article emphasized on collaborative team work involving dental professionals and patients with combination of therapies and regular followup.

Studies on factors associated with etiology of DH suggested possible role of diet, oral habits on enamel wear and subsequent DH.⁴⁸ In the present study during screening phase oral habits and dietary intake of the subjects were recorded, however factors influencing DH was not an objective of the study and so data was not analysed. Minimal invasive procedures should be taken into consideration for management of Dentin Hypersensitivity as patient compliance will be better and reduction in Dentin hypersensitivity scores will be good.^{49,50}

Strength of the study To the authors' knowledge, this is the first study comparing the efficacy of three toothpastes Fluoride containing bioactive glass, fluoride containing tricalcium phosphate and ACP-CCPF in reduction of dentine hypersensitivity. Since no study has compared these 3 toothpastes, direct comparison with similar studies was not possible. However, as the subjects were in supportive periodontal therapy, a longer period of follow up was possible. Both clinical and subjective test were included in this study and the study design was double blinded to reduce the chances of bias. To avoid bias in results due to funding, the study was self-funded and unrevealed to any organisation until the data was analysed.

Limitations of the study

A split mouth design would have given a better insight about efficacy of the toothpaste in reduction of dentine hypersensitivity. As pain threshold differs in subjects and relief of sensitivity might vary to individuals, application of all three toothpaste in each subjects would have resulted in direct comparison for better understanding of the toothpaste efficacy. However, ensuring correct application of the toothpaste to the assigned quadrant in homecare based hypersensitivity treatment is difficult.

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Conclusion

Various in office and home care strategies are available as dentine hypersensitivity treatment. In home care dentifrices are effective means of reducing the sensitivity. Use of bioactive glass gave a better result as compared to tricalcium phosphate and casein phosphopeptide amorphous calcium phosphate fluoride.

DECLARATIONS

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Informed Consent: Written informed consent was obtained from the study participants.

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